

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE SIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *This article discusses the topic of socio-pedagogical factors in the development of professional competence of future sign language teachers based on an integrative approach. The role of the phenomenon of "developing educational environment" in the development of professional competence of future sign language teachers, research on the development of professional competence, their content and essence are revealed. The content of work with hearing-impaired children in the subject of their native language is highlighted.*

Keywords: *approach, sign language teacher, professional competence, content, essence, language, hearing-impaired.*

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, in order to improve the system of continuous education, improve the quality and ensure its effectiveness, along with material factors, the level and potential of developing the professional competence of future sign language teachers are also important. The primary education system plays a special role in creating the necessary conditions for developing the professional competence of future sign language teachers and enabling them to operate in accordance with the requirements of the time.

By teaching students a language, the development of the required standard of skills and abilities in each grade in the four main types of speech activity in this language: listening and understanding speech, speaking, reading and writing, which implies the dynamics of acquiring the skills of independently exchanging and expressing opinions in various speech situations that arise during study, in the work process, in the family, and in public places, perceiving the heard material, as well as obtaining information by reading written sources, and entering into communication in the form of expressing one's attitude to events and phenomena. In modern conditions, the phenomenon of a "developing educational environment" is gaining particular importance in vocational education. It plays an important role in solving the problems of socialization, social adaptation, and the development of future specialists' readiness for professional activity, as noted by Russian and foreign researchers Y.S.Manuylov [1], J.Raven [2], Y.T.Rusakov [3], V.A.Yasvin [4] and others. For example, according to Y.S.Manuylova, if the education system comes into conflict with the environment, it will collapse [1].

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the environment is interpreted as follows:

- a set of natural or social conditions in which life, activity takes place;
- a circle of people related to their profession, work, activity, etc.;
- material conditions in which events, processes, etc. take place [5, 122-b].

As the analysis of definitions shows, the concept of "environment" is revealed through the

categories of space, surroundings, conditions in which human life takes place. Therefore, in essence, it is a factor influencing human life.

V.S. Lednev defines the educational environment of an educational institution as follows: “the educational process assumes the existence of a specially organized didactic (pedagogical) environment, determined by the framework of the requirements of pedagogical technology, limited by the economic capabilities of society and the level of information technologies, meeting the goals and objectives of education” [6. 25-b].

As can be seen from the above definition, the educational environment in a higher educational institution is an integral part of the educational process that affects the development of professional competence of future specialists.

Industrial (pedagogical) practice is a component of the main curriculum of higher professional education and ensures the integration of theoretical and practical training of students with their practical pedagogical activities throughout the entire period of study at a pedagogical higher educational institution. The structure of pedagogical practice, as well as the scientific substantiation of its tasks and functions, are presented in the works of O.A. Abdullina [7], V.A. Slastenin [8] and others.

Many researchers (T.B. Igonina, T.A. Kozhevnikova, T.A. Kryukova, R.M. Sultanova, T.G. Cheshuina, etc.) believe that during the period of production (pedagogical) practice - in the models of future professional activity of students - all components of professional competence are developed, therefore, it is very important to choose the most effective forms and methods of its organization.

Taking into account the above points, we can say that in the process of our work, using the effective forms and methods recommended by the researcher, students will have the opportunity to apply their theoretical knowledge and skills in practice and apply them to their future professional activities.

Thus, as a result of the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, opinions of future sign language teachers, we have identified the following as pedagogical aspects of the group of socio-pedagogical factors: the educational environment of a higher educational institution; forms and methods of organizing the educational process; forms and methods of organizing pedagogical practice.

In the school community, primary school students face various problems in acquiring knowledge and skills in the subject of their native language. This is reflected in the students' learning due to the lack of professional skills and knowledge on the part of the teacher. There are a number of factors that indicate the difficulties of students in acquiring knowledge and the underdevelopment of teachers' professional competencies (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Factors that negatively affect student learning.

We will briefly describe the mentioned subjective personality qualities, determine their impact on the development of professional competence.

According to A.K. Markova, L.M. Mitina and others, the psychophysiological prerequisites of a teacher include: an optimal level of intellectual development, flexibility and convergence of thinking, activity, a high rate of response, lability, emotional stability, a high level of self-control, etc. They ensure the effectiveness of pedagogical activity and a comfortable feeling as its subject [9].

According to I.A. Zimnyaya, one of the main subjective qualities of a pedagogical personality is “personal orientation”, which is an important factor in achieving the peak of professional and pedagogical activity [10].

From a psychological point of view, the orientation of a person is “a set of motives that are stable, independent of current circumstances, express a person’s worldview, and direct human activity in accordance with his interests, inclinations, beliefs, and ideals” [11, p. 230].

Within the framework of this relatively general psychological problem (orientation of a person), researchers A.A. Bodalev, A.K. Markova, V.A. Slastenin, and others study the pedagogical orientation of the teacher’s personality, its psychological content, development conditions, and dynamics.

For example, A.K. Markova defines pedagogical orientation as a motivation (needs, motives, goals, aspirations, etc.) actively directed towards the teaching profession and, above all, towards the development of the student’s personality [12].

Therefore, the reflection of the above-mentioned socially valuable motives in the activities of a future primary school teacher can ensure full and complete unity of upbringing.

The problem of values in pedagogy is studied by D.V. Kiryakova and other scientists in the context of understanding the value orientations of a person, professional orientations. A.V. Kiryakova believes that value orientations at a high stage of development can motivate a person to actions and become his beliefs.

Based on the above considerations, the following conclusion can be drawn. The development of the professional competence of a future surdopedagogue in a higher educational institution should be aimed at developing a value attitude to this process, since only a personally significant value serves as an internal regulator of future professional and pedagogical activity (a stable motive for future professional activity). This indicates that values and value orientations have a significant impact on the process of developing the professional competence of a future sign language teacher in a higher educational institution.

Analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature and questionnaires of students of primary education and sports and educational work allows us to conclude that the psychological aspect in the group of psychological and pedagogical factors influencing the process of developing the professional competence of future sign language teachers is determined by the following factors: psychophysiological foundations of pedagogical activity; motives for choosing a profession; student's inclinations, interests, value orientations.

We identify the remaining subjective qualities of the individual that affect the development of professional competence, namely professional-pedagogical and professional knowledge and skills.

In professional pedagogical knowledge and skills, A.K. Markova separately studies professional knowledge and pedagogical skills. She includes knowledge of pedagogical activity, which has three components in professional knowledge: 1) the teacher's definition of pedagogical goals and objectives; 2) the selection and use of means of influencing students; 3) the teacher's control and evaluation of his or her pedagogical influence (pedagogical analysis). To master pedagogical activity, a future teacher must have pedagogical skills, the foundations of which are developed from the student period. A.K. Markova distinguishes three groups of pedagogical skills corresponding to three groups of professional knowledge [12].

The first group of pedagogical skills: the ability to see a problem in a pedagogical situation and define it as a pedagogical task; the ability to approach the student as an actively developing participant in the educational process with personal motives and goals when defining pedagogical tasks; the ability to study and re-transform the pedagogical situation; the ability to gradually and operationally clarify pedagogical tasks, make optimal pedagogical decisions in conditions of uncertainty, and conveniently reorganize pedagogical goals and tasks during changes in the pedagogical situation; the ability to correctly find a way out of difficult pedagogical situations; the ability to foresee the immediate and long-term results of solving pedagogical tasks, etc. For a student of a pedagogical higher educational institution, the pedagogical situation is the educational situation, that is, the organizational system of variables of the educational process, the psychological basis of which is the interaction, relationships and communication of the teacher with students and students with each other [12].

The second group of pedagogical skills. "What to teach" group: skills in working with the content of educational material; the ability to pedagogically interpret information received from various sources; development of general and special skills and competencies in students, implementation of interdisciplinary connections, etc.

"Who to teach" group: study of individual mental functions in students (memory, thinking, attention, speech, etc.) and holistic characteristics of types of activity (study, work), students' knowledge and upbringing; determination of not only the current level of students, but also the area of proximity to development, the conditions for transition from one level of development to another, the ability to foresee possible difficulties of students and take into account their usual

difficulties; skills in designing and developing levels of activity that do not exist in students; expanding the boundaries of students' self-management; working with weak and gifted students, developing individual programs for them.

Group "How to teach": the ability to jointly select and apply methods and forms of teaching and upbringing, taking into account the expenditure of energy and time of students and the teacher; the ability to compare and generalize pedagogical situations, transfer pedagogical methods to other situations and combine them, apply differential and individual approaches to students, organize their independent educational activities; the ability to find several ways to solve one pedagogical task, to have a variable pedagogical solution.

The third group of pedagogical skills: the ability to apply psychological and pedagogical knowledge and be aware of the modern state of psychology and pedagogy, advanced pedagogical experiences; the ability to time, record, and register the process and results of one's work; the ability to link students' difficulties with shortcomings in one's own work; the ability to see the strengths and weaknesses of one's own work, to evaluate one's individual style, to analyze and generalize one's own experience, to compare it with the experience of other teachers; the ability to build development plans for one's own pedagogical activity.

The subject of the native language is not only a subject that teaches grammatical norms, but also a subject that serves the student's ability to listen and understand texts on an optional topic, in the field of subjects, to read correctly, and to develop orthoepic and orthographic norms. In order for the student to think logically and critically, attention is paid to reading comprehension in native language lessons. A student who has mastered his native language thoroughly will master other subjects satisfactorily. A student with perfect reading literacy will think logically, critically, and creatively by reading the texts he is studying in other subjects, and the ability to apply the knowledge he has acquired in life will be developed.

The subject of the native language is the development of speech (communicative) competence aimed at the student's ability to think, understand the opinions of others, and express his/her thoughts competently in oral and written form; the development of students' acquired knowledge of grammar (phonetics, lexicology, word composition, word formation, morphology, syntax, writing and spelling, punctuation, speech styles, stylistic concepts) and the formation of linguistic competences aimed at developing the ability to express correctly and fluently, making effective use of the wide possibilities of the native language.

The task of native language lessons is to teach hearing-impaired students to practically master the laws of language and use them in connected speech. This task is solved at various levels, such as understanding certain word combinations that express certain meanings; using them in connected speech; systematizing (generalizing) language facts.

The work on the formation of the grammatical structure of speech is divided into the following two stages:

Practical mastery of the basic grammatical laws of the language (classes 1-3);

Practical mastery of grammatical generalizations (classes 4-5);

The formation of students' skills in the active use of connected speech is carried out on the basis of systematic work on revealing the meanings in the grammatical forms of words and grammatical connections connecting words. Various work with words, word combinations, sentences, connected texts allows children to understand the use of the grammatical units being studied and, thus, to increase the level of their mental and speech development.

As a primary language unit, a word combination is taken, in which work is simultaneously carried out on the lexical and grammatical structure of speech. The program provides types and models of word combinations, and based on these types and models, a sentence, which is the main unit of connected thought, is formed in terms of construction.

At the first stage of work on the formation of the grammatical structure of speech, sentence construction skills are formed in such a way that the words in the sentences clarify the meanings of morphological laws. In general, these include laws that are characteristic of nouns (number, case, possession), verbs (tense, person), pronouns (number), adjectives, adverbs, and numbers.

At the second stage of work on the formation of the grammatical structure of speech, certain language facts are systematized. Students are brought closer to generalizing the laws that characterize the features of changing the meaning of nouns, verbs, adjectives, and pronouns. This serves as a transition stage to studying the initial course of grammar (grade 6).

The program, along with the practical mastery of the basic grammatical laws of the language and their systematization (generalization), also involves the introduction of words with different indicators of word formation into connected speech (grade 5). The practical mastery of various word formation models not only helps students increase their vocabulary, but also allows them to better and more fully understand the meaning of words and their interrelationships, and helps them use words correctly.

In classes 1-4, the formation of the grammatical structure of speech is carried out mainly on the basis of simple sentences. Starting from grade 5, the mastery of complex syntactic structures, compound sentence types expressing semantic relations of place, cause, purpose, time and object is also envisaged. In the process of mastering the grammatical structure of the language, students gradually form practical grammatical generalizations. The division of words according to the questions who?, what?, what is doing?, how? (which?) leads to the concepts of "subject", "action", "sign", and then to the more general concept of "word class". The ability to distinguish singular and plural numbers in sentences according to suffixes in noun and verb compounds creates the basis for the grammatical concept of "number". Observing the change of verbs in tenses prepares students to master the concept of "conjugation", and observing the change in the grammatical forms of nouns in sentences according to the change in meaning prepares students to master the concept of "division".

Getting to know the features of the inflection of nouns also helps students master the features of their formation. The concept of inflection complements the lexical-grammatical description of verbs and personal pronouns and clarifies the grammatical features of these word groups.

Gradually, the terms "noun", "adjective", "verb", "pronoun", "adjunct" are introduced.

Along with mastering speech skills and practical grammatical generalizations, students acquire knowledge and skills in spelling, as well as beautiful writing skills. The material presented in the "Grammar and Spelling" section of the program includes the following:

Spelling and punctuation (punctuation marks) – correct writing skills (classes 1-3);

Requirements for the graphic side of writing – husnikhat (classes 1-3). (In this section, the program requirements are given without dividing them into academic quarters).

The speech skills acquired in native language lessons should be used in students' daily learning practice and extracurricular speech practice. On the one hand, this applies to sections in the program that have continuity between them; on the other hand, in native language lessons, students should use the lexical material mastered in speech development and reading lessons.

In general, students are prepared to master the initial course “Grammar and Spelling”, which is allocated in a separate section (grade 4).

The main goal of teaching the native language in primary classes is to develop the oral and written speech of students, as well as their thinking skills and the formation of the schoolchild as a person: to cultivate his civic qualities, interest in knowledge, independence, diligence, responsibility, accountability for work, and the ability to overcome difficulties.

The effectiveness of the mental and speech development of younger schoolchildren depends on their further successful mastering of knowledge in all academic subjects.

The initial course of phonetics, grammar, and spelling covers a wide range of information that is inextricably linked with the content of the native language subject taught in secondary school and relates to various aspects of the native language. Students get acquainted with the phonetic composition of the word, the division of the word into syllables and meaningful parts, almost all word groups and their important forms, the simplest types of sentences, parts of speech and a number of spelling rules.

The program also provides for practical acquaintance of students with the lexical meaning of the word, homonyms, synonyms, antonyms. In the process of mastering the simplest information on phonetics, lexicon, grammar and spelling, children develop thinking skills: analysis, comparison, grouping and generalization of language material, literary speech skills and skills; relationships between the use of basic language units - words, sentences are formed. In the initial course of the native language, the sections “Sounds and letters”, “Word”, “Speech” are considered the most important sections.

Students acquire basic knowledge, skills and skills in sounds and letters in classes 1-3. They learn about sounds and letters and their relationship, vowels and consonants, syllables, stress, sonorous and unsonorous sounds, and learn to perform simple sound-letter analysis of words based on illustrative drawings.

In classes 4-5, abilities and skills in this section are further developed. Sound-letter analysis of words is improved (words are considered together with the spelling), and attention is paid to the development of students' ability to hear speech. This work should be directed primarily to students' mastery of error-free copying, writing down the spoken text, checking what is written, and improving their literacy level. An important program requirement for this section is that children should be able to distinguish speech sounds when they hear them and designate them in writing in accordance with the rules of Uzbek graphics.

Children get acquainted with the fact that writing and pronunciation often do not coincide, which is characteristic of the Uzbek language. They learn the differences in the pronunciation and spelling of voiceless and voiced consonants in words.

In order to strengthen the cognitive activity of children, it is necessary to use a variety of educational tasks involving didactic games, often include interesting exercises and games, and use visual and technical means of teaching.

Based on these considerations, it can be concluded that each group of pedagogical skills allows a person to conduct a general analysis of his current professional activity and see the general aspects of his future professional career, and at the same time develop into a professional specialist from a personal and professional point of view. It is important for a teacher not only to understand the pedagogical situation, but also to organize it, which is an indicator of the teacher's pedagogical maturity.

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